

An Artificial Leaf: a photo-electro-catalytic cell from earth-abundant materials for sustainable solar production of CO₂-based chemicals and fuels

Deliverable D7.4

Communication and Outreach Plan

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document, D7.4 Communication and Outreach Plan, is a deliverable of the **A-LEAF** Project, which is funded by the European Union's H2020 Programme under Grant Agreement No.732840. The Communication and Outreach Plan identifies the main communication objectives of the project and the communication tools and outreach activities that will be defined and implemented in the course of the project according to the target audiences. In addition, this plan defines the responsibilities of the project's participants.

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1 PURPOSE OF THE COMMUNICATION AND OUTREACH PLAN

The A-LEAF Communication and Outreach Plan is one of the deliverables of the WP7: Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication. This document will be regularly (annually) updated as the project progresses:

- D7.4. A-LEAF Communication and Outreach Plan (Month 4)
- D7.12. A-LEAF Communication and Outreach Plan update 12 months
- D7.13. A-LEAF Communication and Outreach Plan update 24 months
- D7.14. A-LEAF Communication and Outreach Plan update 36 months

The main purpose of this deliverable is to provide a formal planning document for the actions that will be done to assure effective communication about the project and its outcomes. The document identifies the main communication tools and outreach activities to be executed during the project according to the target audiences. Finally, this plan will also indicate the responsibilities of the partners and the key messages to be communicated.

In addition to this document, dissemination actions and tools to reach specialized researchers, technologists, industrial actors and policy makers are compiled in the A-LEAF Dissemination and Exploitation Plan and updates (Deliverables D7.3, D7.9, D7.10, D7.11). Concrete measures for internal communication within the consortium members are detailed in the Project Management Book (D6.2). Both deliverables are public and available in the project's website.

2 COMMUNICATION OBJECTIVES

The main goal behind the communication and outreach actions is to contribute to the societal awareness of the new technological results developed by the A-LEAF project. To do so, the Communication and Outreach Plan will schedule different actions aiming to reach general audiences beyond the scientific and industrial communities, with particular emphasis on University and high school students.

The specific objectives of the communication and outreach plan are:

- Project knowledge: actions to raise awareness about the project
- Promotion of project outcomes: actions to announce new results, new publications and patents, attendance to conferences, workshops, etc.
- Dissemination: public disclosure of the progress and results of the project
- Education: increasing public awareness of the environmental benefits of the project involving youngsters and students in science events

3. COMMUNICATION TARGET AUDIENCES

The target audiences that the communication actions aim to reach are divided in the following groups:

- Consortium members
- Scientific community
- Industrial stakeholders
- Other related projects and platforms
- EC and policy makers
- General public
- Students

In the following table it is possible to identify the target audiences and the communication tools more adequate for each of them:

Target Audiences	Communication Tools						Key Messages
	Webpage	Intranet	Social Networks	Press Releases	Newsletter	Videos	
Consortium members					- All key information (documents and reports) to monitor status of the project		
Scientific community			- Advances on scientific knowledge, catalysts and materials, structure-composition-activity relationships				
Industrial stakeholders			- Optimized working conditions, with special emphasis on cost reduction and scalability - New market opportunities, especially for the energy sector				
Other related projects and platforms		- Important advances for the Artificial Photosynthesis research area - Participation of project members and cross-fertilization opportunities					
EC and Policy Makers			- General progress of the project - Legislation, standardisation and development issues				
General Public		- Advances of the project and potential applications of the obtained results - Alternative energy resources					
Students		- Specific knowledge applications within the chemistry, surface, materials and photovoltaics disciplines					

Besides the communication tools described above, other dissemination ones (described in the Dissemination and Exploitation Plan) will be used to reach specialized professionals both from academic and industrial environments, such as: attendance to conferences and industrial fairs, and publications in peer reviewed journals.

4 COMMUNICATION TOOLS

4.1. Project logo and visual identity

A logotype has been designed to advertise the project. The A-LEAF logo is the visual element that represents the project and promotes instant public recognition. The logo was designed with a simple and dynamic look representing a leaf, directly related with the final goal of the project.

The A-LEAF logo together with the EU emblem and the sentence “This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 732840” must be included by all partners in all the communication and outreach documents and events.

4.2. A-LEAF Website

The A-LEAF website has been published under the following url: www.a-leaf.eu. The website is the main online communication tool of the project. It contains information on the project, the consortium and its members, projects achievements and current activities. This information is addressed to all sorts of audiences, from scientists and industrial researchers to the general public.

The website has been designed following a responsive web design (RWD) to enable optimum visualization independently of the size of the screen (PC, tablet and mobile) or web browser one is viewing with. It will be updated frequently as required by ICIQ.

A-LEAF website displays the following sections:

- Home: basic title of the project, banners with the last events/news, access to the other web sections and to the project social networks (Twitter, Facebook and LinkedIn)

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- Project: description of the project and its final goals, timeline, links to related projects, technological platforms and associations
- Consortium: logos of the consortium partners with direct links to the participating research groups webpages
- Outcomes: public deliverables, publications, newsletters, communication and outreach activities
- News & Events: pieces of news and a featured image related to the project events and outcomes
- Press clippings: collection of the media appearances and coverage of A-LEAF news published in general and specialized newspapers and magazines, interviews (radio and TV), videos, etc.
- Contact: information to contact the coordinator
- Jobs: page advertising the job positions available within the project
- Intranet: access to the password protected internal site

4.3. A-LEAF Intranet

The internal part of the website (intranet) can only be accessed by the project's consortium members and has been created to exchange documents, files and other confidential information between the project partners. The intranet will be the main tool for storage and exchange of documents, especially confidential ones, such as:

- Complete contact list including names and e-mail addresses of all the participants
- Templates
- Minutes of the meetings
- Progress reports
- Deliverables

4.4. Social Networks

Social networks will be used to promote the content of the project's webpage, related projects and relevant news related to water splitting and artificial photosynthesis. The project has a profile in each of the following platforms managed by ICIQ.

- Facebook: <https://www.facebook.com/aleaf.h2020>
- Twitter: https://twitter.com/aleaf_h2020
- LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/groups/8599537>

4.5. Newsletters

To further facilitate quick access to the major news and outcomes of the project a newsletter will be prepared by ICIQ (WP leader) every four months to be distributed among the subscribers interested in the project (free subscription available on the webpage – contacts). The newsletters will also be available in the webpage.

4.6. Short Videos

The consortium members will be encouraged to produce short audio-visual material to be freely distributed through the webpage and the institutional YouTube channels of the partners. Scientific concepts and experiments will be communicated from a basic principles perspective to be accessible to the general public.

4.7. Templates and branding elements

Templates for word documents, letters, presentation slides, posters, etc., containing layout and styles used to create standardized documents have been designed to ensure a unified corporate image.

The templates are available in the intranet section of the project's website.

In addition, a roll-up containing the project's logo, title and consortium members is already available (currently stored in the coordinators site) to be used in consortium meetings, workshops, industrial fairs, congresses, etc. as a brand claim.

5. OUTREACH ACTIVITIES OBJECTIVES

In addition to the communication tools described above, outreach activities will also be developed to increase public engagement. The major goal of the outreach activities will be to attract the younger generations to the scientific careers and communicate the advances on the use of alternative energy sources among future end-users.

6. OUTREACH TARGET AUDIENCES

The outreach actions are conceived as educational events and are mainly targeted to students. A-leaf will define specific outreach activities addressed to the following students' communities:

- Primary students
- High school students
- Undergraduate students
- Graduate students
- General public

Most of the A-LEAF participating institutions have already established institutional outreach activities that are periodically run. These on-going activities will be the main venue for promoting A-LEAF. Some of them may also be adapted to the project outreach needs.

The following table shows a summary of the foreseen outreach activities and the target audiences:

Outreach Activity	Target Audience					Organising partner
	Primary students	High school students	Undergraduate students	Graduate students	General public	
Crazy About Chemistry		✓				ICIQ
BIYSC (Barcelona International Youth Science Challenge)		✓	✓			ICIQ
Open doors day		✓			✓	ETHZ
Nanociencia Para Todos (Nanoscience For Everyone)	✓	✓	✓			IMDEA NANO
Semana de la Ciencia de Madrid (Madrid Science Week)	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	IMDEA NANO
WissensDurst Festival				✓	✓	TUWIEN
Imperial Festival	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	ICL
Youth and Science (Artificial photosynthesis course)		✓				ICL
Tag der Neugier			✓	✓	✓	FZ JÜLICH
Open conference at A-LEAF Workshops				✓	✓	ICIQ
Demonstration experiments at the 2nd A-LEAF Workshop			✓	✓	✓	INSTM

7. DESCRIPTION OF OUTREACH ACTIVITIES

A short description of the potential outreach activities that could be included as educational events for A-LEAF can be found below:

Partner	Activity Name	Brief description
ICIQ	Crazy About Chemistry	Chemistry advanced course consisting of special lectures and hands-on experiments for high-school students, organized by ICIQ and the local foundation Catalunya-La Pedrera.
ICIQ	BIYSC (Barcelona International Youth Science Challenge)	International scientific challenge event that aims to connect science students with the best researchers. BIYSC was created by the foundation Catalunya-La Pedrera and ICIQ is one of the research centres participating in the event. In the 2017 edition, ICIQ will prepare a workshop about Artificial Photosynthesis.
ETHZ	Open Doors Day	Annual outreach session organized by the Department of Chemistry and Applied Biosciences of the ETH Zürich. This open doors day aims to facilitate direct contact between ongoing research and the Swiss society.
IMDEA NANO	Nanociencia Para Todos (Nanoscience For Everyone)	Nanociencia para todos is an outreach program that has arisen in response to the demand on popular science activities from the citizens of Madrid. The idea is to promote the creation of links between Science and Society in our region. It consists of specially designed on-demand “Open Day” activities, and outreach talks given in local schools.
IMDEA NANO	Semana de la Ciencia de Madrid (Madrid Science Week)	IMDEA Nanociencia is an active participant in the Semana de la Ciencia de Madrid with a variety of events; public talks, open-days, radio and television interviews -the events are open to all members of the public.
TUWIEN	WissensDurst Festival	Outreach event, organized once a year in Innsbruck, Salzburg and Wien, where several talks are organized in a “Pint of Science” format. Researchers from the local universities and research centres explain their research outcomes in front of a diverse audience.
ICL	Imperial Festival	Imperial College London every year organise a full weekend of open doors at the campus. During the weekend different research groups presents their research to the visitors.
ICL	Youth and Science	This summercamp is organised by foundation Catalunya-La Pedrera. Our group participated in it by developing a two week course for 10 students between 15-16 years old. The whole course is focused on artificial photosynthesis.
FZ JÜLICH	Tag der Neugier	3 Years event organized by the Forschungszentrum Jülich and WDR 5. This open doors day aims to facilitate direct contact between ongoing research and the North Rhine Westphalia society.

In addition to these identified actions, all the A-LEAF partners are encouraged to propose new ones, such as the preparation of learning material about artificial photosynthesis to be freely distributed to high-schools (available in the A-LEAF website). Finally, joint actions are also envisaged during the consortium official meetings or the project's workshops, such as: conferences open to general public, special lectures for graduate students and postdoctoral researchers, demonstration experiments, etc.

8. PARTNER'S RESPONSIBILITIES

All A-LEAF partners must contribute to public engagement and communicate the results of the project to society.

Partners must use the project's logo and EU emblem in all their communications and outreach activities.

ICIQ is the WP Leader of the WP7. Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication. Therefore, regarding the communication and outreach actions, ICIQ will be in charge of:

- Managing and updating the webpage, intranet and social networks
- Releasing the newsletters (every four months)
- Collecting, evaluating and archiving press releases, communication and outreach activities developed during A-LEAF
- WP deliverables preparation
- Informing consortium members about important aspects related with this WP

In addition, each partner will have his/her own responsibilities:

- To prepare the 6-month progress reports where communication and outreach activities will be included when relevant
- To inform and send the coordinator the A-LEAF press releases managed by their institution (at least one)
- To keep a fluent communication with the project coordinator and, whenever possible, provide information and graphic material (such as pictures, posters, leaflets, etc.) of any outreach or communication activities developed within the framework of the project

9. ACTIVITIES EVALUATION

To evaluate the impact of the communication and outreach activities developed during the project different indicators will be collected, such as:

- Number of page views of the A-LEAF webpage (monitored with Google Analytics)
- Number of followers in the different social networks

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- Number of news published in press
- Number of interviews of consortium members in radio/TV
- Number of Newsletters subscribers
- Number of videos related to the project available on the website
- Number of attendees to outreach activities